

Report on the definition and verification of the applicability of simplified parameters to specify the angular behaviour of the CRI for typical indoor lighting and tunnel lighting applications

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In the EMRP Joint Research Project (JRP) "Metrology for Solid State Lighting", the following partners cooperate to create a European infrastructure for the traceable measurement of solid state lighting: VSL (Coordinator), Aalto, CMI, CSIC, EJPD, INRIM, IPQ, LNE, MKEH, NPL, PTB, SMU, SP, Trescal, CCR, TU Ilmenau and Université Paul Sabatier. See <http://www.m4ssl.npl.co.uk/> for more information.

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SUMMARY

The photometric characteristics and performances of luminaires are specified given emitted luminous flux, luminous intensity distribution and luminous efficacy. Some standards require also other parameters, like the luminous flux emitted in peculiar solid angles (as the upward light output ratio R_{ULO}); however these can be deduced knowing the luminous intensity distribution.

In some applications (i.e. road lighting, lighting of working places) standards give requirement also concerning the colour appearance and the colour rendering properties of light. The parameters specified are the correlated colour temperature (CCR) and/or the colour rendering index (CRI).

Other parameters that could be considered are the chromaticity coordinates, the distance from Planckian locus, the spatial colour uniformity and other colour rendering indexes.

With traditional light luminaires these parameters are evaluated considering the lamp data and no particular characterization is required for the luminaire. If SSL luminaires are used, this simple procedure is not satisfactory especially in application where the colour aspects are very important. Due to the optical components used to distribute the light emitted by each LED chips mounted in the luminaire, SSL luminaires could have great differences of the colour properties of the light emitted in different directions.

In these situations, the distribution of the CCR and CRi should be measured, as the luminous intensity. The evaluation of these parameters requires the measurement of the chromaticity coordinates distribution (with colorimeters) or of the relative spectral distribution (with spectrometers). The necessity to developed strategies to manage this great number of data in simple ways is the main aim of this report.

Some measurement carried out on typical luminaires gives examples of the possible ranges of variability of the colour rendering parameters.

The evaluation of the CIE general colour rendering index R_a requires the selection of a reference illuminant. The CIE algorithm describes specific rules for its selection, but these rules could be not the best solution in applications. Some alternative proposals are considered and compared.

In order to reduce the number of directional data, some spatially averaged values are suggested and compared.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

C_{SCCT}	spatial correlated colour temperature code. Set of 6 elements, the first four in kelvin, the last two of dimension 1.
C_{SCNU}	spatial chromaticity non-uniformity code. Set of 4 elements of dimension 1.
C_{SCRI}	spatial colour rendering index code. Set of 8 elements of dimension 1.
C, γ	direction of emission of the light identified by plane C and angle γ on the systems of planes named C -planes, in degree.
$I_v(C, \gamma)$	luminous intensity in the direction C, γ , in candelas.
$I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda, C, \gamma)$	spectral distribution of the radiant intensity in direction C, γ , in watt per steradian per nanometre.
R_a	CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a . Unit 1.
$R_{a,\text{min}}$	minimum value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,\text{Q1}}$	lower quartile (i.e. the 25 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,\text{Q3}}$	upper quartile (i.e. the 75 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,\text{max}}$	maximum value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,\text{std}}$	minimum value, if any, required by a standard or tender of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index. Dimension 1.
$S(\lambda, C, \gamma)$	relative spectral distribution of the radiation in the direction C, γ . Dimension 1.
T_{cp}	value of correlated colour temperature T_{cp} , in kelvin.
$T_{\text{cp},\text{min}}$	minimum value of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.
$T_{\text{cp},\text{Q1}}$	lower quartile (i.e. the 25 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.
$T_{\text{cp},\text{Q3}}$	upper quartile (i.e. the 75 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.
$T_{\text{cp},\text{max}}$	maximum value of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.

$u'(C, \gamma)$	value of the chromaticity coordinate u' in the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, of the radiation emitted in direction (C, γ) . Dimension 1.
u'_{\max}, v'_{\max}	chromaticity coordinate in the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, of the measured colour for which $\Delta E(C, \gamma)$ has its maximum. Dimension 1.
$u'_{\text{ref}}, v'_{\text{ref}}$	chromaticity coordinate in the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, of the colour used as reference for the evaluation of the spatial chromaticity non-uniformity. Dimension 1.
$v'(C, \gamma)$	value of the chromaticity coordinate v' in the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, of the radiation emitted in direction (C, γ) . Dimension 1.
v'_{ref}	value of the chromaticity coordinate v' in the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, used as reference for the evaluation of the spatial chromaticity non-uniformity. Dimension 1.
x	value of the chromaticity coordinate x in the CIE standard colorimetric systems. Dimension 1.
$X(C, \gamma)$	value of the tristimulus X in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric systems, evaluated at the direction C, γ , in lumen per steradian.
$\bar{x}(\lambda)$	first colour-matching functions in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric system. Unit 1.
y	value of the chromaticity coordinate y in the CIE standard colorimetric systems. Dimension 1.
$Y(C, \gamma)$	value of the tristimulus Y in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric systems, evaluated at the direction C, γ , in candelas;
$Z_{p,\text{SCCT}}$	partial spatial correlated colour temperature code.
$Z_{p,\text{SCCT}}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$	element of the partial spatial correlated colour temperature code.
$Z_{p,\text{SCNU}}$	partial spatial chromaticity non uniformity code.
$Z_{p,\text{SCNU}}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$	element of the partial spatial chromaticity non uniformity code.
$Z_{p,\text{SCRI}}$	partial spatial colour rendering index code.
$Z_{p,\text{SCNU}}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$	element of the partial spatial chromaticity non uniformity code.
$Z_{t,\text{SCCT}}$	total spatial correlated colour temperature code.
$Z_{t,\text{SCCT}}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$	element of the total spatial correlated colour temperature code.
$Z_{t,\text{SCNU}}$	total spatial chromaticity non uniformity code.
$Z_{t,\text{SCNU}}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$	element of the total spatial chromaticity non uniformity code.
$Z_{t,\text{SCRI}}$	total spatial colour rendering index code.
$Z_{t,\text{SCRI}}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$	element of the total spatial colour rendering index code.
$\bar{y}(\lambda)$	second colour-matching functions in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric system. Unit 1.
$\bar{z}(\lambda)$	third colour-matching functions in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric system. Unit 1.
$\Phi_{Q1,Ra}$	luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $R_a(C, \gamma) \leq R_{a,Q1}$, in lumen.
$\Phi_{i,Ra}$	luminous flux emitted by the luminaire considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $R_a(C, \gamma) \in [R_{a,Q1}, R_{a,Q3}]$, in lumen.
$\Phi_{s,Ra}$	luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the direction used for evaluating quartiles, where $R_a(C, \gamma) \leq R_{a,\text{std}}$, in lumen

$\Phi_{l,T_{cp}}$	luminous flux emitted by the luminaire considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $T_{cp}(C, \gamma) \in [T_{cp,Q1}, T_{cp,Q3}]$, in lumen.
$\Phi_{e,T_{cp}}$	luminous flux emitted by the luminaire considering all the direction used for evaluating quartiles, where $T_{cp}(C, \gamma) \in [T_{cp,min}, T_{cp,Q1})$ and $T_{cp}(C, \gamma) \in (T_{cp,Q1}, T_{cp,max}]$, in lumen.
$\Phi_{Q2,\Delta E}$	luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $\Delta E(C, \gamma) \leq \Delta E_{Q2}$, in lumen.
$\Phi_{Q3,\Delta E}$	luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $\Delta E(C, \gamma) \leq \Delta E_{Q3}$, in lumen.
Φ_t	total luminous flux of the luminaire, in lumen.
Φ_{γ_1,γ_2}	luminous flux emitted by the luminaire in the spherical delimited by the polar angles γ_1 and γ_2 , in lumen.
$\Delta E(C, \gamma)$	distance, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, between colour with chromatic coordinate $(u'(C, \gamma), v'(C, \gamma))$ and the reference colour with chromatic coordinate (u'_{ref}, v'_{ref}) . Dimension 1.
ΔE_{Q2}	median evaluated considering the values of the distance, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, obtained at the measured directions or in an agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
ΔE_{Q3}	upper quartile (i.e. the 75 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of distance, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, obtained at the measured directions or in an agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
ΔE_{SCNU}	spatial chromaticity non-uniformity. Dimension 1.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BSI	British Standard Institution
CCT	Correlated Colour Temperature
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CIE	Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage
CRI	Colour Rendering Index
EMRP	European Metrology Research Programme
JRP	Joint Research Project
LED	Lighting Emitting Diode

NMI	National Measurement Institute
SCNU	Spatial Chromaticity Non-Uniformity
SSL	Solid State Lighting
UNI	Ente Nazionale Italiano di Unificazione (Italian Standard Organization)

1 INTRODUCTION

The photometric characteristics and performances of luminaires are specified given emitted luminous flux, luminous intensity distribution and luminous efficacy. Some standards require other parameters, like the luminous flux emitted in peculiar solid angles (e.g. the upward light output ratio R_{ULO}), but these can be gathered knowing the luminous intensity distribution.

CEN standards for lighting applications give requirement also concerning the colour appearance and colour rendering properties of the light. For example:

- Regarding sport lighting, EN 12193 [1] specifies values of the correlated colour temperature T_{cp} and minimum and preferred value of R_a . Considering television camera shooting, the maximum permissible deviation of T_{cp} is given too.
- Regarding internal working spaces, EN 12464-1 [2] gives detailed specification for R_a according to the task or activities involved, but considers the colour appearance a matter of psychology, aesthetics and what is considered to be natural. Only for specific applications a restricted range of suitable colour temperature is given.
- Regarding open working spaces, EN 12464-2 [3] follows the same approach of part 1, gives detailed specification for R_a according to the task or activities involved.
- Regarding the exhibition of cultural property, prEN 16163 [4] highlights the importance of correlated colour temperature, particularly at low illuminance level, and of colour rendering. No specific requirements are given because the peculiarity of the lighted objects requires detailed *ad hoc* evaluation of the optimal lighting conditions [5]. National standards, like the British PAS198 [6] follow the same approach.

For road lighting applications some national standards give also requirements considering R_a , for situations in urban and pedestrian areas where the lighting installation design considers primarily the pedestrians needs rather than drivers' or when the mesopic vision concept is applicable [7]:

- The BSI standard for road lighting [8] recommends that the photopic illuminance is reduced using a non-uniform scaling according to the S/P-ratio and adaptation level, so that a larger S/P-ratio allows a lower photopic illuminance, but only when using lamps having $R_a \geq 60$.
- UNI standard for road lighting [9] permits a reduction of one lighting class when using lamps of $R_a \geq 60$ and peripheral vision is important. The designer shall justify this reduction following a risk analysis procedure.

Other parameters, as the distance from Planckian locus and other colour rendering indexes, should be defined and could be calculated using the chromaticity coordinates. If the variation of chromaticity coordinate of the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram (u' , v') in different directions (i.e., with a change in viewing angle) is known the spatial chromaticity uniformity (SCU) can be obtained as the dispersion of these values respect to the average value [10].

The variation of CCT or CRI with the observation angle is not considered in CEN standards because the requirement concerns the lamp data and no particular characterization of the luminaire is required.

Considering traditional luminaires, where variations of CCT or CRI with direction are small and not reproducible, the standard approach avoids peculiar luminaire characterizations with low measurement uncertainty or field measurements. The knowledge of the rated values and eventually the tolerance in manufacturing of lamps is sufficient for verifying agreement with standard requirements.

If SSL luminaires are used, this simple procedure is not satisfactory especially in applications where the colour aspects are very important. Due to the optical components used to distribute the light emitted by each LED chips mounted in the luminaire, SSL luminaires could have great differences of the colour properties of the light emitted in different directions.

In these situations, the distribution of the CCR and CRI should be measured, as the luminous intensity. The evaluation of these parameters requires the measurement of the colour coordinate distribution (with colorimeters) or of the relative spectral distribution (with spectrometers). A measurement solution is described in [11], while the necessity to develop some strategies to manage this great number of data in a simple way is the main aim of this report.

As describe in [11], we consider the situation where for every direction of emission C γ of the light, identified by plane C and angle γ on the systems of planes named C-planes [12], the subsequent quantities are known:

- luminous intensity $I(C, \gamma)$, in candelas;
- relative spectral distribution $S(\lambda, C, \gamma)$ of the emitted radiation, dimension 1;

and chromaticity coordinates, CCR and CRI need to be calculated:

- along a specific direction C, γ ;
- as a directional distribution;
- as spatially averaged value of total spectral radiant flux, to simulate the measurement carried out with an integrating sphere;
- as spatially averaged value of the accumulated spectral radiant flux in zones of the lower and upper hemisphere, to simulate conditions used for defining the CEN flux code [13].

When the chromaticity coordinates are known (see §2), the calculation of colour rendering indices shall be made in accordance to CIE 13.3 [14] or following the suggestions of §3, while CCR can be obtained following one of the algorithms described in literature [15].

Expect for the spatially averaged values, the parameters in all the other conditions can be calculated using exclusively the relative spectral distribution.

The deviation of the colour appearance and the colour rendering properties of light with the angular direction is a very important parameter in applications. Our visual system is able to perceive small differences of colour between adjacent lighted surfaces, but poorly evaluates absolute values for example of CCT.

The spatial chromaticity uniformity (SCU) is measured as the largest deviation of chromaticity coordinate (u' , v') in the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram a LED device emitted in different directions, from its spatially averaged chromaticity (u_a' , v_a') [16] [17]. Usually all data referred to the direction where the luminous intensity is less than 10 % of the peak intensity are ignored in the calculation.

SCU gives a rough description of the real behaviour of the luminaire. For example the largest deviation can be measured in a direction not useful in a given application or represents an anomaly with low influence on the luminaire performances.

To overcome this problem, two approaches are proposed:

- The use of box-and-whisker plots. They are a convenient way of graphically depicts the deviation conditions through their five-number summaries: the smallest value, the lower quartile, the median, the upper quartile, and largest observation. The box-and-whisker plot may also indicates which observations, if any, might be considered as outliers.
- The TTC code, the CRI code and colour uniformity code. Following the idea of the CEN flux code, the average values are given considering the radiant flux in the same spatial zones used in the CEN code.

Of course a combination of the to approaches is possible. They are described in §4.

The evaluation of the CIE general colour rendering index R_a requires the selection of a reference illuminant. The CIE algorithm describes specific rules for its selection, but these rules could not be the best solution in applications. Some alternative proposals are considered and compared.

2 EVALUATION OF CHROMATICITY COORDINATES

The method here described for the evaluation of chromaticity coordinates considers the luminaire characterized by its luminous intensity distribution and its relative spectral distributions at the same angles. The measurement of the luminous intensity distribution is often carried out with illuminance measurements at a known distance. The chromaticity coordinates can be evaluated from these data with the appropriate formula, following the same approach here described.

For a given direction of emission C, γ , the tristimulus values of the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric system can be evaluated as:

$$\begin{aligned} X(C, \gamma) &= K_m \int_0^{\infty} I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{x}(\lambda) d(\lambda) \\ I_v(C, \gamma) = Y(C, \gamma) &= K_m \int_0^{\infty} I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{y}(\lambda) d(\lambda) \\ Z(C, \gamma) &= K_m \int_0^{\infty} I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{z}(\lambda) d(\lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where:

$X(C, \gamma)$ is the value of the tristimulus X in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric systems, evaluated at the direction C, γ , in lumen per steradian.

K_m is the maximum value, in photopic vision conditions, of the luminous efficacy of a radiation, in lumen per watt.

$I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda, C, \gamma)$ is the spectral distribution of the radiant intensity in direction C, γ , in watt per steradian per nanometre.

$\bar{x}(\lambda)$ is the first colour-matching functions in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric system. Unit 1.

$I_v(C, \gamma)$ is the luminous intensity measured at the direction C, γ , in candelas.

$Y(C, \gamma)$ is the value of the tristimulus Y in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric systems, evaluated at the direction C, γ , in candelas.

$\bar{y}(\lambda)$ is the second colour-matching functions in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric system. Unit 1.

$Z(C, \gamma)$ is the value of the tristimulus Z in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric systems, evaluated at the direction C, γ , in lumen per steradian.

$\bar{z}(\lambda)$ is the third colour-matching functions in the CIE 1931 standard colorimetric system. Unit 1.

If $S(\lambda, C, \gamma)$ is the relative spectral distribution of the radiation in the direction C, γ .

$$S(\lambda, C, \gamma) = \frac{I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda, C, \gamma)}{I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda_{max}, C, \gamma)} \quad (2)$$

the tristimulus values can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} X(C, \gamma) &= k(C, \gamma) \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{x}(\lambda) d(\lambda) \\ Y(C, \gamma) &= k(C, \gamma) \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{y}(\lambda) d(\lambda) \\ Z(C, \gamma) &= k(C, \gamma) \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{z}(\lambda) d(\lambda) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where:

λ_{\max} is the wavelength at which $I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda, C, \gamma)$ has its maximum value.

$k(C, \gamma)$ is a normalizing coefficient in candelas

$$k(C, \gamma) = K_m I_{e,\lambda}(\lambda_{\max}, C, \gamma) = \frac{I_v(C, \gamma)}{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{y}(\lambda) d(\lambda)} \quad (4)$$

To evaluate the tristimulus values in a given direction of emission C, γ , the luminous intensity and the relative spectral distribution at the same direction of emission shall be known, while for the chromaticity coordinate only the relative spectral distribution is required:

$$\begin{aligned} x(C, \gamma) &= \frac{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{x}(\lambda) d(\lambda)}{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{x}(\lambda) d(\lambda) + \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{y}(\lambda) d(\lambda) + \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{z}(\lambda) d(\lambda)} \\ y(C, \gamma) &= \frac{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{y}(\lambda) d(\lambda)}{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{x}(\lambda) d(\lambda) + \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{y}(\lambda) d(\lambda) + \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{z}(\lambda) d(\lambda)} \\ z(C, \gamma) &= \frac{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{z}(\lambda) d(\lambda)}{\int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{x}(\lambda) d(\lambda) + \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{y}(\lambda) d(\lambda) + \int_0^{\infty} S(\lambda, C, \gamma) \bar{z}(\lambda) d(\lambda)} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The total luminous flux Φ_t can be derived from the spatial luminous intensity distribution by the formula:

$$\Phi_t = \int_{\Omega_t} I_v(C, \gamma) d\Omega \quad (6)$$

where:

Ω_t is the total solid angle in steradian. $\Omega_t = 4 \pi$.

The luminous flux $\Phi_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2}$ the light source emits in the conical boundary with apex at the centre of the sphere and delimited by the polar angles γ_1 and γ_2 (cone angle) can be obtain with the same formula and the appropriate selection of the solid angle. Of course $\Phi_t = \Phi_{0,180}$.

Following the same approach, the tristimulus values of the spectral radiant flux the luminaire emits in the zone delimited by the polar angles γ_1 and γ_2 , are:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2} &= \int_{\Omega_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2}} X(C, \gamma) d\Omega \\ Y_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2} &= \int_{\Omega_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2}} Y(C, \gamma) d\Omega \\ Z_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2} &= \int_{\Omega_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2}} Z(C, \gamma) d\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The tristimulus values of total spectral radiant flux, to simulate the measurement carried out with an integrating sphere, are obtained with $\gamma_1 = 0^\circ$ and $\gamma_2 = 180^\circ$.

When the tristimulus values are known, the chromaticity coordinate in the CIE colorimetric systems are calculated following the related CIE technical reports (CIE 15 [18] for the commonest cases).

3 CONDITION FOR THE CALCULATION OF THE COLOUR RENDERING INDEX

The CIE 13.3 [14] describes the complete algorithm for the evaluation of the CIE CRI.

One important step of this procedure is the definition of the reference illuminant used for comparing the colour rendering performances of the source to be tested.

The CIE requires:

- the reference illuminant shall be of the same or nearly the same chromaticity as the light source to be tested;
- the reference illuminant for light sources with correlate colour temperature below 5 000 K shall be a Planckian radiator;
- the reference illuminant for light sources with correlate colour temperature equal or greater than 5 000 K shall be one of a series of spectral power distributions of phases of daylight [18];
- for special cases, CIE or other specific standard illuminants may serve as reference illuminant.

The first point is critical in applications. The CIE report specifies the tolerance in the choice of the reference illuminant colour temperature respect to the correlated colour temperature of the light source to be tested.

This approach is correct when a product performance shall be quantified independently by its possible applications. In lighting application, the correlated colour temperature value or range, of the used light source, can be required as part of a tender specification or as part of a pertinent standard, while a minimum value of CRI is specified. In this case, a different procedure is here suggested to evaluate a CRI value really useful:

- in the design phase of a lighting installation for selecting luminaires types and models;
- in the testing phase to verify if the lighting installation performances follow the aims of specifications.

Except for very special installations, the use of the CIE algorithm for the selection of reference illuminant could be considered correct and standards consider it in specifying their requirements. The problem is then clearly limited to the selection of the colour temperature of the reference illuminant. We suggest the following possibilities:

- the CIE proposed values;
- the nominal target value of the correlated colour temperature requested by specifications (standard or tender);
- the minimum and the maximum values (correlated colour temperature range) permissible.

As R_a is an average values its variation considering the different approaches could be relatively small while the singles R_i may shows greater discrepancies, giving a better understanding of the real behaviour of the source in a specific lighting applications.

The increased number of calculations does not represent a limitation of this approach that has the following advantages instead:

- The selection of a value that represents the CCT of the light source considering the dispersion of CCT values with the emission direction has been overcome.
- The comparison between different lighting source is simplified because the CRI values are referred to the acceptable range of CCT that generally is the main parameter to describe the appearance of colour in the given environment;
- Even if not explicitly considered in the CRI evaluation, the influence of tolerances in manufacturing of light source can be roughly estimated. If R_a is always greater than the minimum values required or its spread on a small range of values, the luminaire tolerances can have little effect in the real installation;
- the spread of the CRI values highlights how critical could be the light source in application or the influence of other installation parameters.

4 SPATIAL CHROMATICITY NON-UNIFORMITY

To describe spatial chromaticity non-uniformity (SCNU), the differences between a reference colour and the colours measured at given directions is calculated as the distance, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, between these two colours:

$$\Delta E(C, \gamma) = \sqrt{(u'(C, \gamma) - u'_{\text{ref}})^2 + (v'(C, \gamma) - v'_{\text{ref}})^2} \quad (8)$$

where:

$\Delta E(C, \gamma)$ is the distance, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, between colour with chromatic coordinate $(u'(C, \gamma), v'(C, \gamma))$ and the reference colour with chromatic coordinate $(u'_{\text{ref}}, v'_{\text{ref}})$. Dimension 1.

$(u'(C, \gamma), v'(C, \gamma))$ are the chromaticity coordinate, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, of the measured colour at the (C, γ) direction of emission. Dimension 1.

$(u'_{\text{ref}}, v'_{\text{ref}})$ are the chromaticity coordinates, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, of the reference colour. Dimension 1

Usually the distance at directions where the luminous intensity is less than 10 % of the peak intensity is not calculated. The reference chromaticity coordinates $(u'_{\text{ref}}, v'_{\text{ref}})$ are obtained considering the tristimulus values of total spectral radiant flux $(X_{0,180}, Y_{0,180}, Z_{0,180})$ to simulate an integrating sphere measurement or the averages of the (u', v') values measured.

The spatial chromaticity non-uniformity (SCNU) [16] [17] is measured as the largest deviation of chromaticity coordinates (u', v') in the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram a light source emitted in different directions, from a reference chromaticity $(u'_{\text{ref}}, v'_{\text{ref}})$:

$$\Delta E_{\text{SCNU}} = \max(\Delta E(C, \gamma)) = \sqrt{(u'_{\text{max}} - u'_{\text{ref}})^2 + (v'_{\text{max}} - v'_{\text{ref}})^2} \quad (9)$$

where:

ΔE_{SCNU} is the spatial chromaticity non-uniformity. Dimension 1.

$(u'_{\text{max}}, v'_{\text{max}})$ are the chromaticity coordinates of the measured colour for which $\Delta E(C, \gamma)$ has its maximum. Dimension 1.

$(u'_{\text{ref}}, v'_{\text{ref}})$ is the reference value of the chromaticity coordinate. Dimension 1

This value gives a rough description of the real behaviour of the luminaire. For example:

- the largest deviation can be measured in a direction not useful in a given application or can represent an anomaly with low influence in the luminaire performances;
- no information are given about the real spread of value in all the direction of the uniform chromaticity scale diagram.

To overcome this problem a first approach uses the box-and-whisker plots. They are a convenient way of graphically depicting the deviation conditions through their five-number summaries: the smallest value, the lower quartile (Q_1), the median (Q_2), the upper quartile (Q_3), and largest observation. The box-and-whisker plot may also indicate which observations, if any, might be considered outliers.

From the standard point of view this approach can be simplified considering some conventional decision. For example the SCNU can be evaluated considering the values of the median and of the upper quartile. The accumulated luminous fluxes for all the directions with a value of $\Delta E(C, \gamma)$ lower or equal to median or to upper quartile should be given as useful information for application or comparison of luminaires.

The set of number that specifies these values is called the spatial chromaticity non-uniformity code C_{SCNU} :

$$C_{SCNU} = \left\{ \Delta E_{Q_2}, \Delta E_{Q_3}, \frac{\Phi_{Q_2, \Delta E}}{\Phi_t}, \frac{\Phi_{Q_3, \Delta E}}{\Phi_t} \right\} \quad (10)$$

where:

ΔE_{Q_2} is the median evaluated considering the values of the distance, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, obtained at the measured directions or in an agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.

ΔE_{Q_3} is the upper quartile (i.e. the 75th percentile) evaluated considering the values of distance, on the CIE 1976 uniform chromaticity scale diagram, obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.

$\Phi_{Q_2, \Delta E}$ is the luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $\Delta E(C, \gamma) \leq \Delta E_{Q_2}$, in lumen.

$\Phi_{Q_3, \Delta E}$ is the luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $\Delta E(C, \gamma) \leq \Delta E_{Q_3}$, in lumen.

Φ_t is total luminous flux of the luminaire, in lumen.

This approach could be extended to the CCT and CRI.

If the value of CCT, $T_{cp}(C, \gamma)$ is known for all the measured (C, γ) directions of emission, we are interested to know the limit of their total range, the interquartile range and the correlated fractions of luminous flux. The spatial correlated colour temperature code C_{SCCT} is:

$$C_{SCCT} = \left\{ T_{cp, \min}, T_{cp, Q_1}, T_{cp, Q_3}, T_{cp, \max}, \frac{\Phi_{i, T_{cp}}}{\Phi_t}, \frac{\Phi_{e, T_{cp}}}{\Phi_t} \right\} \quad (11)$$

where:

$T_{cp, \min}$ is the minimum value of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.

$T_{cp,Q1}$	is the lower quartile (i.e. the 25 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.
$T_{cp,Q3}$	is the upper quartile (i.e. the 75 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.
$T_{cp,max}$	is the maximum value of the correlated colour temperature obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions, in kelvin.
$\Phi_{l,Tcp}$	is the luminous flux emitted by the luminaire considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $T_{cp}(C, \gamma) \in [T_{cp,Q1}, T_{cp,Q3}]$, in lumen.
$\Phi_{e,Tcp}$	is the luminous flux emitted by the luminaire considering all the direction used for evaluating quartiles, where $T_{cp}(C, \gamma) \in [T_{cp,min}, T_{cp,Q1})$ and $T_{cp}(C, \gamma) \in (T_{cp,Q1}, T_{cp,max}]$, in lumen.
Φ	is total luminous flux of the luminaire, in lumen.

If the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index, $R_a(C, \gamma)$ is known for all the (C, γ) measured directions of emission, it is interesting to know the limit of their total range of values, the interquartile range and the correlated fraction of luminous flux. Generally standard requires a minimum value of R_a . In this case could be interesting to know the fraction of luminous flux with a R_a lower then the standard requirement. The spatial colour rendering index code C_{SCRI} is:

$$C_{SCRI} = \left\{ R_{a,min}, R_{a,Q1}, R_{a,Q3}, R_{a,min}, R_{a,std}, \frac{\Phi_{Q1,R_a}}{\Phi_t}, \frac{\Phi_{i,R_a}}{\Phi_t}, \frac{\Phi_{1,R_a}}{\Phi_t} \right\} \quad (12)$$

where:

$R_{a,min}$	is the minimum value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,Q1}$	is the lower quartile (i.e. the 25 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,Q3}$	is upper quartile (i.e. the 75 th percentile) evaluated considering the values of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in a agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,max}$	is the maximum value of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained at the measured directions or in an agreed subset of the measured directions. Dimension 1.
$R_{a,std}$	is the minimum value, if any, required by a standard or tender of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index. Dimension 1.
$\Phi_{Q1,Ra}$	is the luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $R_a(C, \gamma) \leq R_{a,Q1}$, in lumen.

- $\Phi_{l,Ra}$ is the luminous flux emitted by the luminaire considering all the directions used for evaluating quartiles, where $R_a(C, \gamma) \in [R_{a,Q1}, R_{a,Q3}]$, in lumen.
- $\Phi_{l,Ra}$ is the luminous flux emitted by the luminaires considering all the direction used for evaluating quartiles, where $R_a(C, \gamma) \leq R_{a,std}$, in lumen
- Φ is total luminous flux of the luminaire, in lumen.

A different approach follows the idea of the CEN flux code [13]. The TTC code, the CRI code and the colour non-uniformity code considering the average values of these quantities are evaluate considering the radiant flux in the same spatial zones used in the CEN flux code.

Table 1 shows the CEN flux code angles that define the zones for the calculation. The accumulated luminous fluxes in these zones are used for the calculation of the utilisation factor tables and are well known in the indoor lighting engineering. The table gives also the limit of the polar angles when different angular steps are used in measurement. The suggestion is to avoid interpolations when measurement results are used to characterize a luminaire.

Table 1 CEN flux code angles and proposed zone code. $\Delta\gamma$ is the angular step adopted for the polar angle increment during measurement. γ_1 and γ_2 are the polar angles defined in eq. 7. For the meaning of x see text.

γ_1 (°)	CEN Standard acronym	Proposed symbol	Standard γ_2 values (°)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 1^\circ$ (°)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 2,5^\circ$ (°)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 5^\circ$ (°)
0	FCL1	$Z_{t,x}(0,40)$	41,4	41	42,5	40
0	FCL2	$Z_{t,x}(0,60)$	60,0	60	60,0	60
0	FCL3	$Z_{t,x}(0,75)$	75,5	75	75,0	75
0	FCL4	$Z_{t,x}(0,90)$	90,0	90	90,0	90
γ_2 (°)	Standard acronym	Proposed symbol	Standard γ_1 values (°)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 1^\circ$ (°)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 2,5^\circ$ (°)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 5^\circ$ (°)
180	FCU4	$Z_{t,x}(90,180)$	90,0	90	90,0	90
180	FCU3	$Z_{t,x}(105,180)$	104,5	105	105,0	105
180	FCU2	$Z_{t,x}(120,180)$	120,0	120	120,0	120
180	FCU1	$Z_{t,x}(140,180)$	138,6	139	140,0	140

Two different types of data could be given:

- **Total average:** the values considering the accumulated radiation in the zones starting from γ_1 in the lower hemisphere and from γ_2 in the upper hemisphere and ending at γ_2 in the lower hemisphere and from γ_1 in the upper hemisphere, as describe in Table 1.
- **Partial average:** the values considering the accumulated radiation in the zones between two adjacent

angular limits as defined in Table 2.

Table 2 Angular limit of the zones when the partial average zone code is adopted. The meaning of symbols is the same of Table 1.

Proposed symbol	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 1^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 2,5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 1^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 2,5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)
$Z_{p,x}(0,40)$	0	0,0	0	41	42,5	40
$Z_{p,x}(40,60)$	41	42,5	40	60	60,0	60
$Z_{p,x}(60,75)$	60	60,0	60	75	75,0	75
$Z_{p,x}(75,90)$	75	75,0	75	90	90,0	90
Proposed symbol	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 1^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 2,5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_2 values for $\Delta\gamma = 5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 1^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 2,5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)	γ_1 values for $\Delta\gamma = 5^\circ$ ($^\circ$)
$Z_{p,x}(90,105)$	104	105,0	105	90	90,0	90
$Z_{p,x}(105,120)$	120	120,0	120	104	105,0	105
$Z_{p,x}(120,140)$	139	140,0	140	120	120,0	120
$Z_{p,x}(140,180)$	180	180,0	180	139	140,0	140

A total zone code is a set of the following 9 numbers, or 4 numbers if the luminaire does not emit in the upper hemisphere:

$$Z_{t,x} = \{Z_{t,x}(0,40), Z_{t,x}(0,60), Z_{t,x}(0,75), Z_{t,x}(0,90), Z_{t,x}(90,180), Z_{t,x}(105,180), Z_{t,x}(120,180), Z_{t,x}(140,180), Z_{t,x}(0,180)\} \quad (13)$$

$$Z_{t,x} = \{Z_{t,x}(0,40), Z_{t,x}(0,60), Z_{t,x}(0,75), Z_{t,x}(0,90)\} \quad (14)$$

A partial zone code is a set of the following 9 numbers, or 5 numbers if the luminaire does not emit in the upper hemisphere:

$$Z_{p,x} = \{Z_{p,x}(0,40), Z_{p,x}(40,60), Z_{p,x}(60,75), Z_{p,x}(75,90), Z_{p,x}(90,105), Z_{p,x}(105,120), Z_{p,x}(120,140), Z_{p,x}(140,180), Z_{p,x}(0,180)\} \quad (15)$$

$$Z_{p,x} = \{Z_{p,x}(0,40), Z_{p,x}(40,60), Z_{p,x}(60,75), Z_{p,x}(75,90), Z_{p,x}(0,90)\} \quad (16)$$

The first step to calculate the generic element $Z_{t,x}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ or $Z_{p,x}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ of the x zone code set is to evaluate the tristimulus values of the spectral radiant flux the luminaire emits in the zone delimited by the polar angles γ_1 and γ_2 (eq. 7).

Three zone codes can be defined (letter x in Table 1 and Table 2):

- The spatial chromaticity non uniformity (x=SCNU), where the generic element $Z_{t,SCNU}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ or $Z_{p,SCNU}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ is:

$$Z_{p,SCNU} = Z_{t,SCNU} = \sqrt{(u'_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2} - u'_{ref})^2 + (v'_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2} - v'_{ref})^2} \quad (17)$$

and $(u'_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2}, v'_{\gamma_1, \gamma_2})$ are obtained from the tristimulus values in the same conditions.

- The spatial correlated colour temperature (x = SCCT) where the $Z_{t,SCCT}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ or $Z_{p,SCCT}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ are the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index obtained from the tristimulus values in the same conditions.
- The spatial colour rendering index (x = SCRI) where the $Z_{t,SCRI}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ or $Z_{p,SCRI}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ are the correlated colour temperature obtained from the tristimulus values in the same conditions.

5 EXAMPLE OF MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The proposed methods have been tested with several different typologies of luminaires.

In particular lamps, luminaires for internal use with direct vision of the LED sources or with diffusing surfaces and luminaires for road lighting and tunnel lighting has been characterized and the proposed parameters and codes texted. 12 different lighting sources have been characterized using the INRIM goniophotometer. They have been classified into five categories:

- lamps;
- luminaires for internal use with partially diffusing surfaces;
- luminaires for road lighting;
- luminaires for tunnel lighting (internal zone);
- luminaires for tunnel lighting (entrance zone).

These luminaires spread the technological evolution during the three years of the project.

The following results are an example of the measurement results. In some cases, tables and diagrams have been reduced in dimensions to improve their legibility.

The measures of the relative spectral distributions are shown in Figure 1 while the differences respect to the direction C180 - $\gamma 0$ can be found in Figure 2. As an example, only some results at different γ angles are given for directions in the C180 plane: the energy in the green part of the spectra increases with the vertical photometric angle.

A set of measured chromaticity coordinates at different C planes and vertical photometric angles is given in Figure 3.

An example of the correlated colour temperature and the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a are shown in Table 3. The correlated colour temperature of the reference illuminants are selected considering the tender specifications of this luminaire. As the minimum value of R_a specified in the tender was $R_a = 70$, it is clear the difficulties to approved the luminaire without clear conventional reference conditions. The luminaire considered shows a very small spread of the values of R_a , because of the average effect of the algorithms used. The measurement uncertainty considers the CIE requirement to specify R_a as integer values.

An example of the correlated colour temperatures versus directions of emission is shown in Figure 4 while the box-and-whisker plot of Figure 5 highlights differences between C planes and gives values for the calculation of specific description codes.

The CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a versus the direction of emission and the correlated colour temperature of the reference illuminant is shown in Figure 6, and as a box-and-whisker plot in Figure 7.

Relative spectral distribution at the given directions of emission

Figure 1 The relative spectral distribution of the tested luminaire at different vertical photometric angles in the C0 – C180 plane.

Difference between the relative spectral distribution at a given direction of emission and the relative spectral distribution at the direction C180 - γ_0

Figure 2 Difference between the relative spectral distribution of the tested luminaire at a given vertical photometric angle and the relative spectral distribution at the polar direction $\gamma = 0^\circ$.

Figure 3 Calculated colour chromaticity coordinates for C planes 0, 90, 180, 270 and vertical photometric angles γ from 0° to 60° (10° step).

Table 3 The values of the main colorimetric parameters versus the direction of emission.

C plane	γ angles	Chromaticity coordinates		Correlated colour temperature	General colour rendering index				
					Ra				
						Reference colour temperature			
		x	y	TCC	5500 K	5750 K	6000 K	CIE algorithm	
[°]	[-]	[-]	[K]	[-]					
0,0 ± 0,1	0,0 ± 0,1	0,320 ± 0,008	0,344 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	10,0 ± 0,1	0,320 ± 0,008	0,344 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	20,0 ± 0,1	0,320 ± 0,008	0,344 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	30,0 ± 0,1	0,321 ± 0,008	0,345 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	40,0 ± 0,1	0,321 ± 0,008	0,346 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	50,0 ± 0,1	0,323 ± 0,008	0,349 ± 0,008	5 900 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	60,0 ± 0,1	0,325 ± 0,008	0,353 ± 0,008	5 800 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	70,0 ± 0,1	0,327 ± 0,008	0,358 ± 0,008	5 700 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
0,0 ± 0,1	80,0 ± 0,1	0,319 ± 0,008	0,349 ± 0,008	6 100 ± 100	67 ± 1	67 ± 1	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	0,0 ± 0,1	0,321 ± 0,008	0,344 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	10,0 ± 0,1	0,319 ± 0,008	0,341 ± 0,008	6 100 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	20,0 ± 0,1	0,318 ± 0,008	0,339 ± 0,008	6 200 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	70 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	30,0 ± 0,1	0,318 ± 0,008	0,338 ± 0,008	6 200 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	70 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	40,0 ± 0,1	0,317 ± 0,008	0,338 ± 0,008	6 200 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	70 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	50,0 ± 0,1	0,317 ± 0,008	0,338 ± 0,008	6 200 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	70 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	60,0 ± 0,1	0,321 ± 0,008	0,345 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	70,0 ± 0,1	0,320 ± 0,008	0,345 ± 0,008	6 100 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
90,0 ± 0,1	80,0 ± 0,1	0,328 ± 0,008	0,359 ± 0,008	5 700 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	0,0 ± 0,1	0,321 ± 0,008	0,344 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	10,0 ± 0,1	0,321 ± 0,008	0,346 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	20,0 ± 0,1	0,322 ± 0,008	0,347 ± 0,008	5 900 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	30,0 ± 0,1	0,324 ± 0,008	0,350 ± 0,008	5 900 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	40,0 ± 0,1	0,325 ± 0,008	0,353 ± 0,008	5 800 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	50,0 ± 0,1	0,327 ± 0,008	0,358 ± 0,008	5 700 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	60,0 ± 0,1	0,319 ± 0,008	0,348 ± 0,008	6 100 ± 100	67 ± 1	67 ± 1	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	
180,0 ± 0,1	70,0 ± 0,1	0,319 ± 0,008	0,349 ± 0,008	6 100 ± 100	67 ± 1	67 ± 1	68 ± 1	67 ± 1	
270,0 ± 0,1	0,0 ± 0,1	0,321 ± 0,008	0,344 ± 0,008	6 000 ± 100	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
270,0 ± 0,1	10,0 ± 0,1	0,322 ± 0,008	0,348 ± 0,008	5 900 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	69 ± 1	
270,0 ± 0,1	20,0 ± 0,1	0,324 ± 0,008	0,351 ± 0,008	5 900 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
270,0 ± 0,1	30,0 ± 0,1	0,325 ± 0,008	0,354 ± 0,008	5 800 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
270,0 ± 0,1	40,0 ± 0,1	0,327 ± 0,008	0,356 ± 0,008	5 700 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
270,0 ± 0,1	50,0 ± 0,1	0,327 ± 0,008	0,357 ± 0,008	5 700 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	
270,0 ± 0,1	60,0 ± 0,1	0,328 ± 0,008	0,358 ± 0,008	5 700 ± 100	68 ± 1	68 ± 1	69 ± 1	68 ± 1	

**Distribution of the correlated colour temperature
at different direction of emission**

Figure 4 The correlated colour temperature at different emission directions. Directions from 1 to 7 are in the C0 plane, 8 to 15 in C90, 16 to 23 in C180, 24 to 32 in C270. In every C plane vertical photometric angles γ start from 0° and have 10° step.

Distribution of the correlated colour temperature

Figure 5 Box-and-whisker plot of the correlated colour temperature at different emission directions.

Figure 6

CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a at different emission directions. Directions from 1 to 7 are in the C0 plane, 8 to 15 in C90, 16 to 23 in C180, 24 to 32 in C270. In every C plane vertical photometric angles γ start from 0° and have 10° step.

Figure 7

Box-and-whisker plot of the CIE 1974 general colour rendering index R_a . From left to right the correlated colour temperatures of the reference illuminant are 5500 K, 5750 K, 6000 K and the temperature selected using the CIE algorithm.

6 CONCLUSION

The peculiarities of LEDs sources require the measurement of the relative spectral distribution versus the direction of emission.

This aspect is very important when luminaires are considered. The optical system (lens or reflectors) used to obtain the wanted luminous intensity distribution can create great variations in the radiometric and colorimetric properties of the emitted radiation. In this case, the measure of the global value obtainable with an integrating sphere is not sufficient to adequately characterize the luminaire in many applications.

Several CEN standard for lighting applications gives requirements on the correlated colour temperature and general colour-rendering index.

A full luminaire characterization gives a great number of spectral data that should be difficult to manage especially when comparison of luminaire has to be done for selections or for defining the best operating conditions.

For this purpose several parameters have been proposed:

- a more general approach for the evaluation of the colour rendering index considering the correlated colour temperature range requested by standards;
- a code that considers the statistical behaviour of the spatial distribution of the chromaticity non-uniformity (C_{SCNU});
- a code that considers the statistical behaviour of the spatial distribution of the correlated colour temperature (C_{SCCT});
- a code that considers the statistical behaviour of the spatial distribution of the colour rendering index (C_{SCRI}).

Following an approach similar to the CEN flux code, a zone code has been proposed following two different limit of the zone. The first solution (total zone) considers the spherical zone starting from the vertical limits while the second (partial zone) considers every zones with two basis. The same parameters are considered:

- the spatial chromaticity non uniformity zone code ($Z_{t,SCNU}$ and $Z_{p,SCNU}$);
- the spatial correlated colour temperature zone code ($Z_{t,SCCT}$ and $Z_{p,SCCT}$);
- the spatial colour rendering index zone code ($Z_{t,SCRI}$ and $Z_{p,SCRI}(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$).

The proposed parameters and codes give an exhaustive and concise characterization of the luminaires with accuracy adequate for industrial applications and correct evaluation of lighting devices.

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